
UTILIZATION OF AI TOOLS IN RESEARCH MANUSCRIPTS: ETHICAL IMPLICATIONS AND CONSIDERATIONS

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Abstract: Artificial Intelligence (AI) is increasingly used to prepare research manuscripts, which improves authorship management and speeds up submission. However, these benefits come with ethical issues. This analysis discusses the risks of AI-generated content, such as bias and factual errors, and the importance of researcher supervision in academic honesty. Transparency in AI use and following protocols are stressed. AI changes peer review, requiring more advanced detection tools and responsible research. By addressing ethical concerns and setting clear guidelines, researchers and journals can use AI to advance research and maintain academic integrity.

Keywords: Commentary, Artificial intelligence (AI), AI generated research, Ethical considerations

Introduction: The domain of research manuscript preparation is rapidly evolving due to the integration of artificial intelligence (AI) and AI-assisted technologies. Many published works endorse the use of AI tools to improve and revolutionize medical research. These tools

offer a diverse array of benefits that go beyond the mere improvement of readability. These tools have the potential to help overcome language barriers, manage time constraints, generate ideas, and facilitate data analysis [4]. However, alongside these advantages, there are significant ethical considerations that require careful attention from researchers and reviewers. In current commentary we aim to address these considerations.

Transforming: Integrating AI tools has improved manuscript preparation and submission speed and made authorship easier to manage. However, are these transformations being appropriately considered? The absence of empirical evidence regarding the quality of AI raises doubts about the credibility of numerous works.

Ethical Considerations: Although artificial intelligence (AI) can be especially useful, relying only on its ability to generate content for creation raises ethical concerns. AI-generated text has the potential to exhibit bias, factual inaccuracies, and a deficiency in the nuanced understanding

that is inherent in human expertise. The problem gives rise to concerns regarding plagiarism and academic dishonesty [2]. It is possible for authors to inadvertently present content generated by computers as their own. To maintain ethical standards, it is imperative for researchers to implement stringent supervision of AI outputs and take full responsibility for the content they present [3].

Transparency: The maintenance of transparency is of paramount significance when utilizing artificial intelligence (AI) tools in the manuscript preparation process. Clearly mentioning the use of artificial intelligence (AI) in the methods section encourages ethical behaviour and allows researchers to understand the inherent constraints of these technologies. This involves explicitly specifying the AI model used, its version, and the rationale behind its implementation. Complying with established protocols, such as those recommended by Nature (which forbids the collaboration of artificial intelligence) and JAMA (which requires precise citation of AI tools), promotes a feeling of confidence among authors, readers, reviewers, and editors [5].

Peer Review: Undoubtedly, the incorporation of artificial intelligence (AI) tools has significantly influenced the peer-review process. While it is feasible to detect specific errors, such as the limitations of AI models, current detection software encounters challenges in differentiating between human authored text and AI-generated content of higher calibre [1]. The situation necessitates the development of more sophisticated detection tools, while

simultaneously emphasizing the importance of responsible research methodologies.

Discussion: There is no doubt that artificial intelligence has enormous potential in research. However, its utilization requires caution and adherence to evolving ethical and methodological frameworks. Journals have a crucial role in creating clear guidelines regarding the use of artificial intelligence (AI), including appropriate situations, and reporting standards. Moreover, it is crucial for researchers to exhibit strict attention to detail in ensuring the genuineness and accuracy of content produced by artificial intelligence. The importance of transparency and ethical considerations in AI research has been emphasized by recent incidents in the field, specifically through the supervision of authors. The implementation of clear and specific guidelines and protocols is crucial for upholding integrity in the field of AI research.

Looking ahead, it is imperative to address potential future roadblocks. By engaging in open and clear conversations and adhering to clear ethical guidelines, scholars and academic publications can effectively employ artificial intelligence (AI) to accelerate research progress while maintaining academic integrity. The collaborative effort is essential in ensuring diligent and dependable scientific communication.

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